

The Alan Turing Institute

Cyber Threat Observatory for National Identity Systems

**Quarterly Report: Drawing Insights from
Vulnerability Patterns in Digital Identity,
Government, Healthcare, and Finance
Sectors**

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Cyber Threat Observatory for national identity systems

The programme's flagship observatory focuses on offering timely insight and analysis of cyber threats that have potential to negatively impact identity systems globally.

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Executive Summary

This report, produced by the Turing Cyber Threat Observatory, presents an in-depth analysis of Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs) across four foundational domains of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI): Digital Identity, Finance, Health, and Government. Drawing on data from the National Vulnerability Database (2020-2024), the investigation examines reported CVE and their associated Common Weakness Enumerations (CWE) to identify cross-sectoral security weaknesses that, if exploited, could compromise the confidentiality, integrity and availability of systems and undermine the broader trustworthiness of DPIs [1]. By analysing vulnerabilities and their underlying causes and visualising the vendors and products reported, the analysis seeks to inform security strategies for digital identity platforms and the broader digital public infrastructure.

Key Findings

Using methodically and rigorously developed filters and keyword-based classification, the report highlights a sustained increase in sector-specific vulnerabilities.

- Digital identity exhibited the most pronounced growth, with CVEs increasing from 290 in 2020 to 569 annually by 2024, reflecting both its increased adoption and its growing exposure to security threats.
- Healthcare and Government sectors experienced a threefold increase in reported CVEs between 2020 and 2024. This trend appears to be driven by rapid digitisation, increased exposure of legacy systems, and greater transparency in citizen-facing services.
- The Finance sector showed year-to-year fluctuations, with an initial spike in CVEs followed by overall stability, possibly due to more mature vulnerability management practices.

The cross-sector recurrence of CWEs reveals systemic weaknesses, particularly in authentication, session management, access control, and input data handling. These weaknesses are especially concerning where digital identity systems are deeply embedded within sectoral services, creating potential for transitive risks across the broader DPI. Some of these CWEs include:

- CWE-20: Improper Input Validation [2]
- CWE-79: Cross-site Scripting [3]
- CWE-89: SQL Injection [4]
- CWE-269: Improper Privilege Management [5]
- CWE-287: Improper Authentication [6]
- CWE-862: Missing Authorization [7]
- CWE-863: Incorrect Authorization [8]
- CWE-918: Server-Side Request Forgery [9]

The report also classifies CVEs by attack vectors (*Network, Local, Adjacent Network, Physical*), showing a dominance of remote (*Network*) threats, particularly affecting finance and digital identity platforms. However, *Local* and *Physical* attack surfaces—especially in health and government—are increasingly relevant due to on-premise systems and biometric interfaces.

Visual mappings using Sankey diagrams trace CVEs from assigners to vendors and products, uncovering concentrated risks in platforms such as Oracle FLEXCUBE (Finance), Cisco Identity Services (Digital ID),

and custom hospital systems (Health). These charts reveal vendor dependencies, fragmented disclosure practices, and standardisation gaps that complicate coordinated defence.

Implications for Digital Public Infrastructure

- Continuous cross-sector threat modelling and risk assessment for secure design and operation against recurring CWEs and CVEs. The frequent occurrence of authentication and authorisation-related CWEs suggests the need for sustained investment in secure development practices.
- The overlap of CWEs between sectors underscores the value of cross-domain vulnerability awareness, particularly for shared identity services, middleware, and interoperability frameworks, where a weakness in one domain could introduce systemic exposure. Continuous monitoring is required on upcoming CVEs being reported and published.
- Besides external *Network*, attack vector classification reveals consistent CVE associations with *Adjacent Network*, and *Local* vectors, indicating the importance of securing internal processes and communications beyond traditional perimeter control of the network.
- Strengthening the security posture at the design levels by incorporating CWE - informed assessments - can help mitigate known weakness patterns. Policy-level support for secure-by-design standards in digital identity components is essential for trustworthy DPI.

Ultimately, the findings position digital identity systems as critical national infrastructure, not only vulnerable in their own right but also as amplifiers of risk across Finance, Health, and Government. As DPI adoption accelerates globally, especially in low- and middle-income countries, this report offers a strategic blueprint to understand and mitigate cross-sector cybersecurity risks in an increasingly interconnected world.

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1 Background and Motivation

Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) encompasses the foundational digital systems that enable essential services for society – notably Digital identity (ID) platforms, government e-services, healthcare information systems, and financial technologies. As these systems become deeply interwoven, their security is paramount to ensure public trust and safety. Globally, digital threats continue evolving, exposing systemic challenges in private and public infrastructures. Identity fraud remains a significant threat, with losses in the US reaching \$20 billion in 2022. Recent studies also point to a rise in synthetic identity fraud and reuse of stolen credentials, with numerous identity records involved in multiple breaches [10; 11]. The impact extends beyond monetary loss, as identity misuse increasingly enables account takeovers and lateral movement across digital services [12]. The number of victims have generally been consistent or growing from year to year [13]. Meanwhile, breaches in the public sector have continued notably, with 584 confirmed data disclosures among more than 3,200 incidents reported in 2023 [14]. There has been a marked increase in breaches motivated by multiple threat actors, highlighting the ongoing risk to citizen data held by the Government [14]. Targeted ransomware and data extortion campaigns have disproportionately affected public sector institutions that lack incident disclosure frameworks [15; 16]. Despite growing awareness, vulnerability disclosure policies (VDPs) remain under-implemented across organisations, limiting coordinated remediation [17; 18].

A significant contributor to the increase in incidents is the persistent exploitation of structural weaknesses such as in the Application Programming Interface (API), which forms the foundation of modern digital services. Recent analysis shows numerous API-based attacks are linked, according to known Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) vulnerabilities, with misconfigurations and weak access controls being the most common reasons for these attacks. In the past year, 99% of organisations experienced API related incidents and 57% were deemed vulnerable [19; 20]. This expanding role of API chains, particularly in healthcare and financial services, increases the range of successful exploits [21; 22]. Recent MOVEit platform vulnerabilities illustrate how supply-chain embedded APIs enable threat actors to traverse multiple trust zones [22]. Such patterns are a growing concern when organisations have indicated that they had delayed the implementation of a new application due to concerns about API security [23]. These trends highlight the urgent need for real-time monitoring, posture governance, and authentication mechanisms. These figures also reveal systemic Common Weakness Enumerations (CWEs) in the system that adversaries may exploit in future attacks.

The widespread adoption of federated identity and single sign-on (SSO) architectures compounds these risks. For example, compromising a single identity provider may have consequential effects across dependent services. Critical security incidents involving providers such as Microsoft and Okta illustrate the broader implications of vulnerability in the identity infrastructure, highlighting the need for well-audited authentication ecosystems [24].

Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI), the foundation of scalable identity, payment, and data services, is expanding rapidly across nations. India has emerged as a global leader in this space, deploying DPI platforms such as Aadhaar, UPI (real-time payments), and DigiLocker (document storage), all of which are integrated into Government, Financial, and welfare ecosystems [25]. These platforms now serve over a billion people, executing billions of monthly transactions and enabling digital services at an unprecedented scale. Multiple developing countries are studying and adopting India's DPI model to bypass traditional infrastructure models [26].

However, this growth comes with an expanding attack surface. DPI systems, especially Digital ID platforms, are deeply interconnected across sectors, linking government benefits, banking services, health records, and more. A vulnerability in one sector (for example, a health portal or financial API) can become a pivot point in the identity layer. The presence of CWE patterns such as Improper Authentication and Incorrect Authorization in identity systems, alongside SQL injection and Session Mismanagement in others, shows clear cross-sectoral risk propagation. Digital ID systems, once compromised, can be used to access or impersonate users across domains, turning them into threat amplifiers. This interconnectedness underscores the fragility of scale. A sectoral API or data store breach can cascade across identity-linked services, degrading societal trust in digital systems [27]. As countries replicate India's DPI model [26], these risks become globalized — particularly where rapid adoption outpaces regulation and local cybersecurity capacity [28].

The motivation for this report is to equip policymakers, analysts, and architects with sector-specific threat intelligence drawn from the National Vulnerability Database's Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) and CWE patterns. We classify vulnerabilities by their CWE, attack vector, and sectoral context to uncover weaknesses that could be exploited. This includes mapping how vulnerabilities flow from assigners to vendors, products, and attack methods, highlighting systemic exposure points. Analysis of CVE trends reveals a dominance of design-level weaknesses such as CWE-79 (Cross-Site Scripting), CWE-287 (Improper Authentication), and CWE-89 (SQL Injection), with notable sectoral differences [29]. This reinforces the need for CWE-focused remediation tailored to context rather than one-size-fits-all controls.

Finally, this report emphasises the need to shift from reactive mitigation to proactive security strategies informed by CWE. These include:

- **Cross-sector vulnerability analysis** to identify shared weakness classes and their implications for Digital ID system;
- **Attack vector analysis** to prioritise defences by exploitation method.

The threat landscape is further complicated by the advent of generative AI, which adversaries can now use to create convincing synthetic identities and bypass biometric verification systems [30]. These tools amplify traditional attack vectors and undermine trustworthiness in remote authentication, particularly in high-assurance sectors like finance and healthcare.

In summary, the security of Digital ID systems has evolved beyond merely being an access-related concern; it now forms a fundamental part of national priorities. As developing countries accelerate the adoption of DPIS, this report offers a model for understanding and managing the vulnerabilities accompanying scale and interdependence.

2 Introduction

As the foundation of modern digital governance, DPIs increasingly depend on complex interconnected systems where security is essential to maintaining societal trustworthiness. The social impact of DPI security failures can be profound, as the erosion of trust in a Digital ID provider can jeopardise the perceived reliability of entire digital governance ecosystems [12; 27]. Central to this infrastructure are Digital ID systems, critical enablers of authentication, authorisation, and access management. A compromise in these systems can cascade across sectors. Understanding how vulnerabilities spread within and across these domains is, therefore, vital to protecting national and transnational digital ecosystems. This concern is underscored by recurring vulnerabilities, which have been exploited across both public and private systems [29; 21]. To this effort, the following key objectives were formulated:

- Identify CVEs relevant to each sector through contextual keyword filtering and analysis of CVE metadata, including product, vendor, and description fields.
- Map CVEs to their associated CWEs to examine recurring weaknesses and identify sector-specific and cross-sectoral vulnerability trends.
- Analyse vulnerabilities by attack vector classification (e.g., Network, Local, Adjacent Network, Physical) to understand likely the pathways.
- Visualise the relationships between the CVE assigners, vendors, and affected products using tools to support the exploratory analysis of the vulnerability distribution.
- Consider implications on Digital ID platforms within DPI.

This report presents a multisectoral vulnerability analysis centred on Common Vulnerabilities and Enumerations (CVEs), enhanced through Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) mappings and contextualized using sector-specific filtering logic. This methodology reflects an evolution from traditional CVE counting toward weakness-driven prioritization strategies, which are increasingly recommended in threat intelligence frameworks [31; 32]. Drawing on data from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) covering the period from 2020 to 2024, the study focuses on vulnerabilities relevant to three foundational domains of the Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI): Digital ID, Finance, Healthcare, and Government.

CVEs are evaluated against each sector using a keyword-based conditional logic methodology that scans the CVE descriptions, associated products, vendors, and mapped CWEs. A single CVE may align with multiple sectors if its characteristics span domain boundaries. To maintain clarity in visual representations and to acknowledge the interconnected nature of modern systems, CVEs are counted independently within every sector that they match. This non-exclusive assignment approach captures cross-sectoral relevance: for example, a vulnerability affecting authentication mechanisms may be critical to both the financial and Digital ID domains. Government platforms, especially those handling citizen records and benefits systems, face consistent threats involving improper access controls (CWE-863) and unpatched open-source components [33; 15]. In federated ID ecosystems, weaknesses in SSO protocols and token mismanagement (e.g., CWE-613: Insufficient Session Expiration) introduce attack vectors that extend across identity providers and relying parties [24; 12]. Such mapping also highlights the ripple effects of a compromise in federated identity systems, which increasingly act as authentication backbones for healthcare and financial services [24; 30].

To ensure transparency, a flag system was used in the code logic: CVEs were evaluated against each sector filter logic separately and only included if they satisfied both the inclusion and exclusion conditions. Thus, the alignment is rule-based rather than probabilistic. This is especially important for public sector systems that often are underfunded and are challenged in implementing structured VDPs, making timely CVE triage and remediation more difficult [17; 18].

To enhance the CWE analysis, the report visualises the inter-dependencies using Sankey diagrams that trace the flow of vulnerabilities from CVE assigners to vendors, specific products, and finally to the associated *attack vectors*. These visual mappings provide intuitive, evidence-backed illustrations of how specific product lines –such as Oracle’s FLEXCUBE in Finance, Cisco’s Identity Services in Digital ID, or hospital

management systems in Health – serve as recurrent targets of sector-specific exploitation patterns. In the healthcare sector, legacy systems and insufficient access control have led to the recurrence of vulnerabilities such as CWE-284 and CWE-306 (Missing Authentication for Critical Function), which remain under-patched despite known exploit patterns [34; 22]

They also uncover hidden inter-dependencies between vendors and services that span sectors, highlighting systemic risk concentrations. For instance, recurring flaws in systems like Oracle FLEXCUBE illustrate how banking platforms are consistently targeted for their central role in financial transactions and data management [21]. Furthermore, this helps in understanding the validity of the data set and the vulnerability mappings in detail. For example, the 2023 MOVEit breach demonstrated how a widely used file transfer system vulnerability cascaded through multiple health networks, exposing systemic risk inherent in shared platforms [22; 35].

The analysis is quantitative and interpretive, designed to support operational decision-making, policy formulation, and vulnerability management. This perspective aligns with the 2024 ENISA foresight report, emphasising the shift from incident-driven models to anticipatory cybersecurity grounded in systemic design insights [31]. It is important to note that the existing literature lacks this type of approach or studies. This novel approach is particularly relevant for DPIs, where vulnerabilities, such as authentication and access control (e.g., CWE-287, CWE-863), are increasingly entangled with injection flaws and data exposure vulnerabilities originating in adjacent domains and sectors. Emerging technologies such as generative AI further complicate the security landscape, enabling scalable impersonation attacks and deepfake-aided identity fraud, particularly in remote verification contexts [30].

The remainder of this report is organised as follows.

- **Section 2: Methodology** - Details the multistage filtering, keyword logic and CWE validation framework used to extract and refine sector-relevant CVEs.
- **Section 3: Results and Analysis** – Provides sector-specific CVE timelines and CWE distributions, with deep dives into Digital ID and grouping of insights from Finance, Health and Government. The section also classifies threats by the *Network*, *Local*, *Adjacent Network*, and *Physical* vectors, contextualising proximity and mode of exploitation.
- **Section 4: Strategic Considerations** – Explores the implications of the findings on Digital ID systems and the larger Digital Public Infrastructure.
- **Section 5: Conclusion** - Summarises key insights and calls for a cross-sectoral alignment of threat intelligence.
- **Appendix A** – Includes Sankey diagrams for each sector, offering granular visibility into assigner-vendor-product-vector links.

3 Methodology

The primary data source for this study is the NVD, which provides detailed CVE records. Each CVE entry includes rich metadata, severity scoring through CVSS (Common Vulnerability Scoring System), vulnerability classification via the CWE, and references to affected products and associated vendors.

The dataset spans a five-year period from 2020 to 2024 to ensure a meaningful trend analysis. This timeframe allows the identification of evolving patterns, recurring weakness types, and sector-specific attack vectors. The CVE data are acquired in JSON format and processed through a multistage data pipeline to produce a clean, structured dataset for analysis.

Table 1 outlines the complete methodology. The pipeline includes ingestion, cleaning, transformation, vulnerability enrichment (e.g. CVSS and CWE standardisation), stakeholder-specific risk classification (via SSVC) and domain-focused filtering. It also incorporates frequency-based analysis using Bag-of-words [36] to identify the most impactful CWEs across critical sectors such as Digital ID, Finance, Health, and Government.

This methodology ensures standardised data consistency, completeness and contextual relevance to the targeted domains. The resulting structured dataset enables sector-specific and cross-sector vulnerability analysis and trend visualisations.

Table 1: Methodology Overview for Sector-Specific CVE Analysis

Step	Phase	Description
1	Data Ingestion	Ingests CVE data in JSON format. Extracts structured information including CVE IDs, publication and update dates, affected vendors/products, and CVSS/CWE attributes. Supports diverse input formats using flexible parsers. Outputs raw CSV files.
2	Data Cleaning	Cleans raw CSV files by replacing missing values with "N/A", entries, and logging file-specific errors. Cleaned files are saved with a cleaned_ prefix, and sample outputs are provided for verification.
3	Data Structuring	Standardises and enriches CVE data across multiple dimensions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metadata: CVE ID, State, Assigner, Date Reserved, Date Published, Date Updated• Product Information: Vendor, Product, Version• Descriptions and Titles: Description, Title, References

4	Data Standardisation	<p>Parses and normalises both CVSS v3.x and v4.0 fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core Metrics: CVSS Base Score, CVSS Severity, CVSS Vector String • Attack Vectors: Attack Vector, Attack Complexity, Privileges Required, User Interaction • Impact Metrics: Confidentiality Impact, Integrity Impact, Availability Impact • Scope and Requirements: Security Scope Changed, Attack Requirements • CVSS v4.0 Fields: Safety Impact, Safety Availability Impact • CWE Classification: CWE ID, CWE Description <p>Incorporates stakeholder-specific metrics for risk prioritization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSVC Exploitation • SSVC Automatable • SSVC Technical Impact • SSVC Role • SSVC Version
5	Deduplication	<p>Applies a two-stage deduplication method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregates all unique CVE IDs across files • Filters master dataset by these unique identifiers <p>Ensures full retention of associated vulnerability details and metadata.</p>
6	Final Dataset Schema	<p>The structured dataset includes the following columns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CVE Metadata: CVE ID, State, Assigner, Date Reserved, Date Published, Date Updated • Product Info: Vendor, Product, Version, Less Than Version • Descriptions: Description, Title, References • CVSS Metrics: Base Score, Severity, Vector String, Attack Vector, Complexity, Privileges, User Interaction, Security Sc, CIA Impacts, Attack Requirements, Safety Impact (v4.0), Safety Availability Impact • CWE Fields: CWE ID, CWE Description <p>SSVC Metrics: Exploitation, Automatable, Technical Impact, Role, Version</p>

7	Domain-Specific Filtering (Refer Table 3)	Implements keyword-based filtering to isolate Digital ID vulnerabilities. Inclusion categories: authentication, authorisation, verification, passwords, tokens, breaches, biometrics, etc. Excludes unrelated domains such as IoT and industrial control systems. Please refer to Table 3
8	Sector-Based CWE Analysis	Identifies top 10 most frequent CWEs per sector (Government, Finance, Health, Digital ID) through frequency analysis. Highlights dominant vulnerability types within each domain.
9	CWE Consolidation and Trend Visualisation	Combines top CWEs from all sectors into a unified set. Tracks trends from 2020–2024 via time-series analysis and visualisation to identify emerging and persistent vulnerability patterns.

3.1 Data Ingestion

The data ingestion phase serves as the foundational step in the processing pipeline, responsible for acquiring and organising raw vulnerability data. The primary data source is the NVD, which publishes CVEs in JSON format. These files are retrieved in bulk and stored in a designated input directory for automated processing.

Each CVE JSON entry is parsed to extract essential fields, including:

- **CVE ID:** The unique identifier for each vulnerability.
- **Publication and Update Dates:** Temporal markers that allow for longitudinal analysis.
- **State and Assigner:** Metadata indicating the publication status and responsible organisation.
- **Affected Products:** Vendor, product, and version information specifying the impacted systems.
- **CWE ID:** The unique identifier that maps each CVE to a CAPEC weakness.

By consolidating raw CVE data into a consistent format, the ingestion step establishes a reliable format for subsequent processes such as cleaning, transformation, and enrichment. This structured approach enables reproducibility and facilitates large-scale sector-specific vulnerability analysis.

3.2 Data Cleaning

The data cleaning stage addresses inconsistencies and quality issues in the raw CVE data extracted during ingestion. It operates on pre-filtered CSV files using a parser capable of handling diverse delimiters and formats. Missing values are standardised using a consistent placeholder (e.g., “N/A”), and any malformed lines are skipped while maintaining error logs for transparency and reproducibility. For each file, a sample of the cleaned data is displayed for verification, and a standardised version is saved with a cleaned_ prefix to preserve the original input. This process ensures the generation of a clean, consistent dataset that forms a reliable dataset for subsequent transformation, enrichment, and analysis stages.

3.3 Data Structuring

In this stage, the CVE data is structured to standardised tabular format suitable for analysis. This phase begins with the extraction of core metadata, including CVE ID, state, assigner, and temporal fields such as reservation, publication, and update dates. The affected product information, including the vendor, the product name, the version, and the comparative versioning fields, is also consolidated to support the scope of vulnerabilities. The transformation process extends to the interpretation of vulnerability descriptions and

references, ensuring contextual completeness. Additionally, the pipeline parses CVSS vector strings from both versions 3.x and 4.0, mapping them to normalised metrics including base score, severity level, attack vector, complexity, privilege requirements, user interaction, and impact across confidentiality, integrity, and availability. This structured representation facilitates consistent comparisons and downstream filtering while preserving all relevant vulnerability attributes for enrichment and trend analysis.

3.4 Data Standardisation

This stage focusses on the standardisation of vulnerability scoring and classification systems, specifically the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) and the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE). The pipeline supports both CVSS version 3.x and the newer version 4.0 by parsing their respective vector strings and mapping them to a consistent set of severity metrics. These include the CVSS base score, severity level, attack vector, attack complexity, privileges required, user interaction, scope changes, and impacts on confidentiality, integrity, and availability (the CIA triad). For CVSS v4.0, additional fields such as safety impact and safety availability impact are also captured. In parallel, the pipeline extracts and maps CWE identifiers to standardised descriptions that classify the underlying vulnerability type. This practice enables consistent severity assessment and comparative analysis across multiple years and sectors, forming a critical input for trend visualisation and sector-specific risk profiling.

3.5 Data Integration

The integration of Stakeholder-Specific Vulnerability Categorisation (SSVC) enhances the depth of the dataset by incorporating risk prioritisation metrics. SSVC provides a structured format to assess the urgency and relevance of vulnerabilities based on real-world exploitation potential and operational impact. During this stage, the pipeline extracts and standardises SSVC fields such as exploitation status, technical impact, role, version, and automation potential. These attributes offer critical insight beyond traditional severity scoring, allowing for more nuanced prioritisation based on stakeholder needs. By embedding SSVC metadata alongside CVSS and CWE information, the data set supports multidimensional risk assessments, making it particularly suitable for sector-specific threat modelling and vulnerability management strategies. This study understands the potential of SSVC; however, it will be considered for further research.

3.6 Deduplication

The deduplication stage ensures the uniqueness of the dataset by eliminating redundant CVE entries. This is implemented through a two-stage process. First, the pipeline aggregates all unique CVE identifiers from a collection of pre-filtered CSV files, handling inconsistencies such as date formatting issues using coercive error handling. Second, these unique identifiers are applied to the main dataset to retain only one complete instance of each vulnerability. Throughout this process, all associated metadata, severity scores, and classification details are preserved. The resulting output is a consolidated, non-redundant dataset that provides a reliable foundation for sector-based analysis and longitudinal trend evaluation.

3.7 Final Dataset

The final dataset is a structured, deduplicated, and enriched CSV files that integrates all relevant CVE attributes necessary for detailed vulnerability analysis. Each record includes metadata such as the CVE ID, state, assigner, and temporal markers (reservation, publication, and update dates). Product information captures vendor, product name, version. The dataset also includes textual fields such as description, references, and advisory titles. CVSS metrics are standardised across both version 3.x and 4.0, covering base score, severity, vector strings, attack vector, complexity, privileges required, user interaction, scope, and impacts on confidentiality, integrity, availability, and safety. CWE classifications are included via CWE ID and human readable descriptions. Lastly, the dataset integrates SSVC fields for exploitation status, technical impact, automation potential, and stakeholder role. This comprehensive schema supports robust, multi-dimensional analysis of vulnerabilities across time and sectors.

3.8 Domain-Specific Filtering

A consistent keyword-based filtering process was applied across all sectors — Finance, Healthcare, Government, and Digital ID — to classify relevant vulnerabilities. Each sector used a custom set of inclusion and exclusion keywords, combining domain-specific terms (see Table 3). CVE records were retained only if they matched at least one relevant domain term and one technical mechanism, ensuring contextual and operational relevance. Irrelevant domains such as Internet of Things (IoT), Industrial Control System (ICS), gaming, and unrelated consumer technologies were excluded based on frequency analysis and manual review. For example, Digital ID filtering focused on terms like authentication, credentials, and identity platforms. Similar logic with relevant sector-specific terms was applied for other sectors. This approach ensures that each dataset is both focused and comparable, enabling meaningful cross-sector analysis. CVEs were allowed to appear in multiple sectors to reflect shared infrastructure and interdependencies.

3.8.1 Sector Definitions

Each sector is defined based on a combination of functional relevance, keyword matches, and vendor/product classification. Sectoral boundaries are not mutually exclusive — for instance, a CVE affecting a hospital ID system may appear in both Health and Digital ID domains.

- Finance: Systems related to banking, mobile payments, transaction processing, account access, or financial middleware.
- Healthcare: Systems related to hospitals, patient portals, EMRs, health information exchanges, or medical device software.
- Government: Platforms used in public administration, digital governance portals, public services, municipal systems, or national e-government platforms.
- Digital ID: Systems or services enabling authentication, identity verification, SSO, identity APIs, biometrics, tokens, or credential issuance — regardless of the hosting sector.

CVE overlaps are maintained to reflect shared infrastructure and interdependencies.

3.8.2 Keyword Filtering Strategy

A core component of this methodology is the keyword-based filtering mechanism. For each sector, a curated list of inclusion and exclusion keywords is constructed to capture sector-specific system contexts and threat themes. This set of keywords is informed by domain knowledge, past vulnerability patterns, and terminology extracted from CVE. The frequency of keywords was also calculated and used for filtering.

Each CVE record is scanned across multiple fields—description, product name, and associated CWE text—to identify keyword matches. A record is retained only if it satisfies inclusion criteria and does not contain any exclusion terms. Logical operations (AND, OR, NOT) are applied to refine the scope and minimise false positives.

During exploratory filtering, high-frequency but irrelevant terms (e.g., “church”, “blood”, “router”, etc.) were flagged by the Bag-of-Words frequency analysis as contributing to off-domain CVEs. Manual inspection revealed patterns such as:

- “Church” appearing in spiritual ID platforms unrelated to national identity services
- “Blood” frequently referring to transfusion apps, not applicable to Finance
- “Router” entries overwhelmingly tied to enterprise or home networking vulnerabilities, skewing Digital ID and Government results

These terms were added to exclusion filters after repeated false positives were detected. Each was documented and validated through full-text review.

3.8.3 Filtering and Selection Process

The keyword filtering approach is semi-automated. Initial keyword sets were generated using frequency analysis (Bag-of-Words). These were iteratively refined through manual inspection and snowballing (e.g., checking linked CVEs and adjust filters). While effective for current scope, future iterations may incorporate machine learning-based classifiers to scale filtering with minimal human intervention. Table 2 summarises the filtering stages, from initial extraction to final data set preparation.

1. **Raw Data Retrieval:** CVE records from NVD datasets (2020–2024) were extracted.
2. **Keyword Screening:** Sector-specific filtering was applied using inclusion / exclusion terms (refer to Section 3.8.4). These inclusion and exclusion was determined by using Bag of Words python library to determine the frequency of keywords.
3. **Full-Text Evaluation:** Validated with manual verification and retained CVEs for contextual fit.
4. **Snowballing and Human Feedback:** Refine filters through iterative review and analysis of linked vulnerabilities using keywords.
5. **Final Selection:** Export validated CVEs for sector-specific reporting and visualisation.

An overview of the operational stages of filtering is summarised in Table 2, which outlines each processing step from data extraction to final inclusion.

Table 2: Threat Intelligence Workflow

Stage	Description for Digital ID Systems	Outcome
Threat Intelligence Query Execution	Extracts threat data from NVD CVE 2024, 2023, 2022, 2021, 2020	Raw dataset of threats: CVE 2024 (29,248), CVE 2023 (28,682), CVE 2022 (25,169), CVE 2021 (22,823), CVE 2020 (20,524)
Screening (Keyword Matching)	Formulated and implemented filtering using: Filter 1 (DPI Digital ID - 140 keywords), Filter 2 (DPI Financial - 42 keywords), Filter 3 (DPI Health - 30 keywords), Filter 4 (DPI Government 12 keywords). Refer to Table 3 for further details.	Refined threats to Digital Identity, Financial, Government & Health
Inclusion/Exclusion (Full Text Analysis)	Removes non-relevant security findings, retains critical vulnerabilities	Final refined dataset for detailed review: Digital Identity, Financial, Government, Health
Backward Snowballing & Feedback	Identifies related threats through references and links. Feedback loop: Adjust screening criteria based on false positives, missing patterns, and new emerging threats.	Expanded intelligence from interlinked threats. Improved screening accuracy for future iterations.
Final Inclusion	Prepares structured threat intelligence	Final dataset ready for analysis & visualisation

3.8.4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure relevance and data quality, the following inclusion and exclusion criteria are applied:

- **Inclusion:**

- CVEs containing one or more inclusion keywords in relevant field, as formulated in Table 3.
- CVEs associated with a recognised CWE classification.
- CVEs published between January 2020 and December 2024.

- **Exclusion:**

- CVEs containing any exclusion keywords.
- CVEs lacking full descriptive information or valid CWE mappings.
- CVEs associated with unrelated sectors (e.g., gaming, automotive, IoT, industrial systems).

Table 3: Keywords used to filter CVE data

Sector	Combined Filtering Condition (Keywords)
Digital Identity	<p>Inclusion: authentication, authenticate, authorisation, authorization, authorise, authorize AND identity, identities, account, accounts, admin, access AND one or more of: user, users, IdP, Kerberos, login, IAM, active directory, LDAP, OAuth, OIDC, SSO, SAML, RBAC, ABAC, privilege escalation, password, passkey, MFA, 2FA, OTP, TOTP, U2F, FIDO, biometric, fingerprint, face, iris, WebAuthn, hijacking, session, token, certificate, JWT, PKCE, credential, unauthorized, unauthenticated, bypass, IDOR, CSRF, Okta, Auth0, Microsoft Entra ID, Google Identity, Apple Sign-in, AWS IAM, Keycloak, ForgeRock, Ping Identity, IBM Security Verify, OneLogin, CyberArk, HashiCorp Vault, Ivanti</p> <p>Exclusion: router, routers, IoT, ECU, printer, printers, camera, cameras, industry, industries, industrial, game, games, robot, robots, SCADA, microSCADA, IIoT, industrial control system, embedded system, hospital, vehicle, vehicles, infotainment, car, tour, travel, energy, power, marketing, business, ventilator, school, student, bounty, IIm, dashboard, exam, media, booking, hotel, video, animation, latex, podcast, audiobook, jupyter, child, food, restaurant, lms, word press, WordPress, WP, hugging face, transformer, transformers, signal, fuel, XWiki, trading, simantic, Electronics, church</p>
Healthcare	<p>Inclusion: doctor, doctors, patient, patients, prescription, prescriptions, vaccine, vaccines, healthcare, health, medicine, medical, pharmacy, pharmacies, disease, diseases, hospital, hospitals, telemedicine, teledoc, pharmaceutical, blood, organ, donation, donor, clinic</p> <p>Exclusion: linux kernel, shop, cryptocurrency, print and scan doctor</p>

Finance	Inclusion: pay, paid, payment, money, cash, finance, financial, bank, banking, stock, stocks AND one or more of: blockchain, management, transaction, transactions, trade, trading, coin, coins, identities, identity, market, markets, operation, operations, operational, product, products, service, services, account, accounts, insurance, fraud, crime, swift, visa, mastercard, debit, credit Exclusion: blood, graphql
Government	Inclusion: government, governments, citizen, citizens, ministry, ministries, nation, nations, national, democracy, organisation, organization

3.8.5 Validation

To enhance reliability, each selected CVE is evaluated through its associated CWE. We examine whether the described weakness aligns with operational realities in the sector. Where feasible, we map CWEs to the MITRE ATT&CK framework to highlight adversarial relevance.

We also track keyword coverage, CWE distribution, and filtered vendors, assigners, and products to assess the precision of each sectoral filter. Feedback loops are introduced to iteratively improve keyword sets and reduce false positives.

CVE data is inherently shaped by disclosure practices. Open-source ecosystems tend to disclose vulnerabilities more transparently (e.g., GitHub, VulDB), whereas proprietary systems may underreport due to vendor discretion or regulatory gaps. The Government sector may be underrepresented due to restricted disclosures or internal remediation without public CVE assignment. These imbalances affect sectoral CVE counts and should be considered when interpreting results.

3.9 Output and Use Cases

The outcome is a curated, dataset of CVEs for each sector. Each entry is enriched with metadata (e.g., CWE ID, severity score, publication date), and filenames are dynamically generated based on filtering parameters. These datasets are suitable for integration into operational security dashboards, vulnerability management platforms, and strategic cyber risk assessments.

This methodology supports decision makers, security architects, and policy makers in identifying and responding to vulnerabilities that are specifically relevant to their sector. By combining automated keyword filtering with technical validation through CWE analysis, and following the multistage process outlined in Table 2, the approach ensures that attention is focused on threats that matter, improving the efficiency and precision of cyber risk management in healthcare, financial and public service infrastructures.

4 Results and Analysis

The filtering process applied to CVE records from 2020 to 2024 yields distinct sectoral patterns in vulnerability counts (Figure 1). Digital ID systems surfaced as the most affected, with a consistent and sharp increase throughout the years, from 67 CVEs in 2020 to more than 520 in 2023 and 2024. This likely corresponds to the expanding use of identity technologies and greater reporting activity in this area.

The Health sector also showed a notable upward trajectory, reaching its peak at 208 CVEs in 2024, more than tripling from its 2020 count. This may reflect the continued digitisation of healthcare systems, increased vulnerability disclosure processes.

The Government sector demonstrated a steady increase in vulnerabilities over the years, rising tenfold from 6 CVEs in 2020 to more than 60 in 2024. This indicates both expanded exposure to digital services and possible improvements in disclosure or detection practices.

In contrast, Finance sector results displayed more variation, with an initial increase in 2020 (86 CVE), followed by a dip and stabilising at 50 CVE in 2023 and 2024. This pattern may be attributed to sector-specific disclosure timelines, consolidation of financial platforms, or fewer CVEs reported later in the years.

In general, keyword-based filtering reveals variation in reported CVE volumes across sectors and highlights trends over time. This underscores the importance of sector-specific mitigation efforts, particularly in areas showing rapid growth such as Digital ID and Health.

Figure 1: CVE results per sector based on filtering (2020–2024)

4.1 Sector: Digital Identity

Given its high volume of CVEs, the Digital ID sector is analysed separately using monthly and quarterly breakdowns to offer a more granular view. Whereas the Government, Health, and Finance sectors are

grouped together to account for overlap and shared vulnerabilities involving identity systems. Two distinct views provide insight into the evolving CVE threat landscape.

- Monthly CVE reports (2020–2024): Figure 2 graph shows a consistent upward trajectory in digital ID CVEs, with notable acceleration from mid-2023 onwards. The peak occurs in November 2024 with nearly 80 CVEs reported, indicating heightened disclosure and analysis activity in this domain.
- Quarterly CVE Reports (2020–2024): Figure 3’s broader view reinforces the trend of escalating threats, with steady increases each year. Q4 2024 emerges as the most active quarter, surpassing 175 reported CVEs.

Figure 2: Monthly Trend of Reported Digital ID CVEs (2020–2024)

Figure 3: Quarterly Trend of Reported CVEs Related to Digital ID (2020–2024)

The volume of CVEs associated with Digital ID systems has increased substantially between 2020 and 2024, signalling an increasing level of threats to identity infrastructure. What began as a relatively low activity domain in 2020 has evolved into one of the most active vulnerability spaces by the end of 2024. This growth

trajectory is evident across both monthly and quarterly reporting intervals, indicating not only a surge in discoveries, but also a maturing and increasingly transparent disclosure process.

From early 2020 through mid-2023, the number of CVEs associated with Digital ID systems increased steadily, with occasional periods of volatility. However, from late 2023 onwards, there was a marked acceleration. Monthly reports peaked in November 2024, nearing 80 disclosed CVEs, while quarterly data showed an all-time high of over 180 CVEs in Q4 2024. This surge likely reflects a combination of increased system usage, broader integration of identity tools across sectors, and improvements in vulnerability reporting and disclosure practices.

The consistent increase in CVEs each quarter - with no significant drop-offs - reflects both the growing complexity of Digital ID ecosystems and improved awareness among vendors, researchers, and system integrators. The upward trend also points to more structured vulnerability management workflows, including coordinated disclosures and possibly regulatory or compliance-driven pressure to address latent security flaws. Rather than sporadic or event-driven spikes, the data shows a sustained increase in volume, underscoring the ongoing and evolving risk profile of Digital ID platforms.

Strategically, this data has critical implications. Security and IT teams operating digital ID infrastructures should expect increased traffic on their vulnerability management programmes. The trend indicates that threat actors could be targeting identity mechanisms such as authentication, session management, and role-based access systems. Operational teams must be prepared for peak activity, when disclosures tend to spike. Continuous monitoring, proactive patching, and real-time incident response frameworks are essential to managing this expanding threat surface. Furthermore, cross-sector collaboration will be key, as Digital ID vulnerabilities often intersect with broader domains such as Health, Finance, and Government.

These patterns suggest a growing dependence on Digital ID platforms, real-time monitoring, and a maturing vulnerability disclosure ecosystem.

4.2 Sectors: Government, Finance, Health

These Government, Finance and Health sectors highlight comparative trends without allowing the high volume of CVEs in Digital ID to mask lower-volume patterns. While their CVE counts are modest compared to Digital ID, meaningful distinctions in their trajectories are still visible.

- **Monthly Trends (2020–2024):** Figure 4 shows monthly CVE activity across Government, Finance, and Health remains relatively low, with the Health sector showing intermittent spikes. Notably, a sharp rise occurred in Health in October 2024, which stands out but requires further investigation to determine whether it reflects sustained change, coordinated disclosure, or an isolated event. Finance shows a mild upward drift, while Government remains largely consistent with low variance.
- **Quarterly Trends (2020–2024):** On a quarterly basis (Figure 5), Health shows the clearest upward trend, peaking in Q4 2024. This could indicate increasing sectoral focus or policy-driven reporting changes in the late 2024 or there could be an increased number of CVEs. However, given the volatility in the monthly data, this Q4 spike needs to be further investigated.

Figure 4: Sectors: Monthly CVE Trend

Figure 5: Sectors: Quarterly CVE Trend

Between 2020 and 2024, the Government, Finance and Health sectors exhibited various patterns in CVE reporting, with a lower overall volume than the Digital ID sector, but with notable variations. While these sectors typically function independently, they often share infrastructure components—particularly identity systems—making the CVE trends relevant for evaluating shared exposure patterns.

The Health sector stands out among the three, especially in the latter half of the observed period. From 2020 through 2022, CVE reporting remained relatively modest and sporadic. However, 2023 and 2024 showed a clear upward trend, culminating in a sharp spike in Q4 2024, where nearly 100 vulnerabilities were revealed.

This surge may be driven by legacy system exposure, increased vendor transparency, and regulatory shifts that require a greater disclosure of vulnerabilities. The consistent appearance of vulnerability spikes throughout this period suggests that the Health sector is transitioning from reactive security practices to more routine and possibly mandated reporting [37; 35].

The Finance sector presents a different profile. While active in 2020 and 2021 with frequent monthly peaks, this did not result in a sustained upward trend. However, this activity did not translate into a consistent upward trend. Instead, the sector showed intermittent surges, notably in Q3 2022 and Q3 2024, but maintained a

relatively flat average over the five-year span. This pattern may reflect the use of centralised platforms or regulatory bottlenecks in disclosure. Alternatively, it could stem from a reliance on third-party services whose vulnerabilities are reported under broader classifications [38; 21; 39].

The Government sector showed the lowest and most consistent CVE volume throughout the five-year period. Minor variations occurred, with modest increases in 2022 and 2023, but the overall trend remained flat. The data indicate either a conservative disclosure posture or slow operational cycles for patch validation and publication [18]. This may reflect stricter internal remediation policies, cautious disclosure practices, or slow adoption of public vulnerability reporting standards [28; 17].

Although CVE volumes vary across sectors, there is a clear increase in reported threats, especially in Health in the late 2024. Strategically, this comparison underscores the importance of interpreting low CVE volume with caution. Limited disclosures may not indicate low risk, however, instead suggest underreporting or lack of consistent monitoring in the sectors. Lower disclosure does not necessarily imply lower risk; it may also point to underreporting, legacy dependence, or lack of active monitoring. The sharp escalation in Health CVEs in late 2024 highlights how critical infrastructure sectors can face sudden increases in disclosed vulnerabilities. A proactive, cross-sector CVE monitoring strategy is crucial—particularly where shared identity systems enable authentication and data access across domains.

4.3 Attack Vectors

This section analyses the types of attack vectors associated with disclosed CVEs across four critical sectors—Government, Finance, Health, and Digital ID—between 2020 and 2024. By classifying CVEs according to the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) attack vector taxonomy, we assess the dominant exploitation pathways and exposure surfaces within each sector.

An attack vector, as illustrated in Figure 6, describes the pathway through which a vulnerability can be exploited, as defined by the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [29]. Classifying vulnerabilities by attack vector helps assess an attack surface of a sector and understand how threats can spread, whether through *Network*, *Local*, or *Physical* [32]. The Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) defines four primary attack vectors, each representing different levels of attacker proximity and access requirements [32]:

- *Network*: The vulnerability can be exploited remotely on a network, such as the Internet, without requiring physical or local access. This includes flaws in exposed web services, remote APIs, and public-facing applications.
- *Adjacent Network*: Exploitation requires the attacker to be on the same local or logical network segment as the target system (e.g., LAN, Wi-Fi, or subnet). These vectors typically involve limited-range attacks such as ARP spoofing, Bluetooth exploits, or VLAN hopping.
- *Local*: The attacker must already have access to the system or obtain it through other means (e.g., through a legitimate user account or compromised credential). Vulnerabilities in this category often relate to privilege escalation, file manipulation, or insecure local configurations.
- *Physical*: The attacker needs physical access to the target device or environment to exploit the vulnerability. This includes attacks involving hardware tampering, USB payloads, or direct interaction with on-premise infrastructure such as biometric modules or access control panels.

4.3.1 Government Sector

The Government sector shows a mixed attack surface, with *Network* and *Adjacent Network* vectors being the most frequently observed. Network based CVEs appear consistently across the timeline, reflecting exposure in externally accessible systems such as citizen portals and public services. A mid-2023 spike in *Adjacent Network* vector CVEs may indicate increased reporting of vulnerabilities related to *Local* network infrastructure, potentially related to segmentation or configuration weaknesses. *Local* and *Physical* vectors remain limited but show occasional activity, suggesting low-volume insider threats or misconfigurations on endpoint systems.

4.3.2 Finance Sector

Vulnerabilities reported in the Finance sector are predominantly associated with the *Network* vector, highlighting the sector's reliance on exposed APIs and web-facing services. Spikes in March, August, and October 2024 may reflect clustered disclosures related to shared technologies or regulatory reporting cycles, rather than coordinated exploitation. Other vectors, including *Local* and *Physical*, appear rarely, which aligns with the remote-first architecture and centralised platforms typical of financial environments.

4.3.3 Health Sector

Network based vulnerabilities dominate the healthcare sector and show an upward trend, culminating in a dramatic spike in November 2024. This surge may reflect increased disclosure from vendors or the emergence of clustered injection vulnerabilities (e.g., SQL, LDAP). *Local* and *Adjacent Network* vectors also appear, suggesting vulnerabilities that could be exploited within hospital networks or by authenticated users. Though minimal, *Physical* vector CVEs highlight potential weaknesses in connected medical devices and on-site systems.

4.3.4 Digital ID Sector

CVE data for Digital ID systems shows a consistent increase in vulnerabilities with the *Network* vector, reflecting the high exposure of authentication platforms and session management services. There is also a gradual increase in CVEs tied to *Local* and *Adjacent Network* vectors, indicating broader exposure across internal identity workflows and infrastructure. Although *Physical* vector CVEs are rare, their presence is notable due to the role of hardware tokens and biometric authentication in modern identity platforms.

Attack Vectors
 ● NETWORK ● ADJACENT_NETWORK ● LOCAL ● PHYSICAL

Figure 6: Attack Vectors identified among different sectors (Network, Adjacent Network, Local, Physical)

4.4 Common Weakness Enumeration

This section identifies the most prevalent CWEs across sectors by first extracting the top 10 CWEs per sector (Government, Finance, Health, Digital ID) based on frequency (Table 4). The CVE system catalogues are publicly known cybersecurity vulnerabilities, each assigned a unique identifier. In contrast, the CWE categorises the underlying software or hardware weaknesses that can lead to such vulnerabilities. Each CVE entry may be linked to one or more CWEs, offering a standardised way to understand the root causes of security issues on different systems.

CWEs are merged into a unified list to track cross-sectoral and temporal patterns. This consolidated set of CWEs is then used to create consistent visualisations that track the temporal evolution of these vulnerabilities from 2020 to 2024. Analysing top CWEs enables identification of both sector-specific and cross-sector security weaknesses, offering a deeper view into the underlying causes of reported vulnerabilities. While high CWE frequency does not directly equate to exploitability or real-world impact, repeated occurrences of the same weakness type across CVEs can indicate persistent security gaps and systemic risk patterns within or across sectors.

The distribution of CWEs (Table 4) in key sectors from 2020 to 2024 reveals distinct patterns and highlights shared weaknesses that can be exploited across domain boundaries. The Digital ID and Health sectors show the highest CWE volume and diversity. Finance exhibits moderate frequency with narrower concentration, while Government displays a broader but less dense distribution. Based on the CWE graphs across sectors from 2020-2024, the following subsections provide a detailed insights across sectors.

Based on the Table 4, the most common weaknesses fall into three primary categories: authentication and authorization flaws (e.g., CWE-287, 285, 862, 863) Add [29; 40; 12], input validation and injection issues (e.g., CWE-79, CWE-89, CWE-20), and access control or exposure weaknesses (e.g., CWE-284, 200, 639).

Table 4: Cross-Sector CWE Threats Relevant to Digital ID Systems

CWE ID & Name	Sector & CWE Count
CWE-20: Improper Input Validation	Government (4), Health (5)
CWE-79: Cross-Site Scripting (XSS)	Government (23), Finance (14), Health (82), Digital ID (38)
CWE-89: SQL Injection	Finance (27), Health (150), Government (5)
CWE-200: Information Exposure	Government (8), Finance (6), Health (6), Digital ID (44)
CWE-269: Improper Privilege Management	Government (11)
CWE-284: Improper Access Control	Government (11), Finance (5), Health (7), Digital ID (52)
CWE-285: Improper Authorization (Deprecated)	Government (7), Finance (2), Digital ID (85)
CWE-287: Improper Authentication	Health (7), Digital ID (165)
CWE-288: Authentication Bypass Using an Alternate Path	Digital ID (36)
CWE-306: Missing Authentication for Critical Function	Digital ID (79)
CWE-352: Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF)	Finance (3), Health (19)
CWE-502: Deserialization of Untrusted Data	Health (5)
CWE-639: Insecure Direct Object Reference (IDOR)	Government (8), Finance (4), Digital ID (75)
CWE-707: Improper Enforcement of Message Integrity	Finance (2)

CWE-798: Use of Hard-coded Credentials	Health (6)
CWE-862: Missing Authorization	Government (7), Finance (10), Health (8), Digital ID (94)
CWE-863: Incorrect Authorization	Government (9), Finance (5), Digital ID (142)
CWE-918: Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF)	Government (4)

4.4.1 Government Sector

Although the Government sector reports lower CVE volumes, its associated CWEs span a diverse range of weaknesses, suggesting exposure across multiple system components.

- **CWE-79 (XSS)**, **CWE-284/285 (Access Control/Authorisation)**, and **CWE-200 (Information Exposure)** dominate, especially from 2023 onwards.
- The presence of **CWE-918 (SSRF)** and **CWE-20 (Improper Input Validation)** highlights exposure through public APIs, open portals, and backend systems.
- CVE volumes increase from 2022 to 2024, likely reflecting both digitisation of citizen services and more consistent vulnerability disclosures [33; 15].
- In general, vulnerabilities suggest a combination of ageing infrastructure and newer, partially hardened digital services [33; 15].

4.4.2 Finance Sector

The Finance sector shows a concentrated set of recurring CWEs, particularly those affecting data handling, session integrity, and access logic in financial applications.

- **CWE-89 (SQL Injection)** once again leads with 27 CVEs, targeting payment processing, transactional APIs, and financial databases.
- **CWE-79 (XSS)**, **CWE-862 (Missing Authorisation)**, and **CWE-200 (Information Exposure)** point to risks in multilayered architectures with exposed microservices or customer portals.
- **CWE-352 (CSRF)** and **CWE-639 (IDOR)** signal logic vulnerabilities in transaction workflows and account management systems.
- The steady distribution of CVEs mapped to high-impact CWEs suggests continued discovery and disclosure of vulnerabilities in financial platforms.

Figure 7: CWE Distribution by Sector (2020–2024): Sector-wise CVE counts highlight respective dominant and growing CWE patterns

4.4.3 Health Sector

Healthcare's CWE profile is dominated by input validation failures, injection flaws, and misconfigurations—many affecting EHR platforms, legacy portals, and embedded systems.

- **CWE-89 (SQL Injection)** dominates with 150 CVEs, posing threats to patient data, EHR systems, and third-party integrations [34].
- **CWE-79 (XSS)** and **CWE-352 (CSRF)** reveal the risk of session manipulation and user interface based on the UI, likely driven by legacy portals and patient-facing applications [34].
- **CWE-284 (Access Control)** and **CWE-862/863 (Authorisation flaws)** remain consistent over the years, indicating persistent weaknesses in access enforcement [22; 41].
- **CWE-798 (Use of Hard-coded Credentials)** and **CWE-502 (Deserialisation of Untrusted Data)** suggest poor security hygiene in embedded systems and integration of medical devices.
- Healthcare CWEs peaked in 2024, aligning with increased digitisation efforts and potential sector-wide compliance shifts [34; 22; 41].

4.4.4 Digital ID Sector

Digital ID systems are dominated by CWEs related to authentication, authorization, and access control enforcement—underscoring their systemic importance and exposure.

- **CWE-287 (Improper Authentication)** leads with 165 CVEs, underscoring a systemic failure to reliably validate identity tokens and sessions.
- **CWE-863 (Incorrect Authorisation)** and **CWE-862 (Missing Authorisation)** closely follow, revealing gaps in privilege enforcement and user role validation.
- **CWE-285 (Improper Authorization)**, **CWE-306 (Missing Authentication for Critical Function)**, and **CWE-284 (Access Control)** highlight weak or inconsistent enforcement of access controls.
- **CWE-639 (Insecure Direct Object Reference)** and **CWE-200 (Information Exposure)** indicate the exposure of sensitive data through insecure object references and poor boundary enforcement.
- **CWE-79 (Cross-Site Scripting)** appears throughout the timeline, targeting session hijacking and UI manipulation.
- **CWE-288 (Authentication Bypass Using an Alternate Path)** signals logical flaws in authentication mechanisms, potentially through unprotected APIs or alternative access channels.
- Trends from 2020 to 2024 show a steady increase in CVEs linked to authentication flaws, likely reflecting increased deployment of federated identity services and more scrutiny by researchers.

Figure 8: Top CWE Threats per Sector (normalised percentage of global max)

4.5 CWEs relevant to Digital ID Systems

The Table 5 identifies CWE categories that are not currently dominant in Digital ID systems but appear prominently in adjacent sectors such as Health, Finance, and Government. These weaknesses may represent latent exposure pathways due to the deep integration of digital ID platforms into Health, Finance, and Government systems. Given the cross-sectoral role of identity systems—often embedded in authentication flows for healthcare and financial platforms—CWEs prominent in those sectors may indicate future exposure trends for identity infrastructures.

Table 5: Cross-Sector CWE Threats Relevant to Digital ID Systems (Expanded)

CWE ID & Name	Observed Sector(s) & Counts	Relevance to Digital ID
CWE-20: Improper Input Validation	Health (5), Government (4)	Introduces risk in user-facing workflows such as login, registration, or identity proofing, where input handling is critical.
CWE-79: Cross-Site Scripting (XSS)	Health (82), Finance (14), Government (23), Digital ID (38)	May allow session hijacking or script injection in identity flows, particularly on login, token exchange, or profile pages.
CWE-89: SQL Injection	Health (150), Finance (27)	Threatens identity databases and session stores; may enable credential theft, privilege escalation, or unauthorized account access.
CWE-200: Information Exposure	Health (6), Finance (6), Government (8), Digital ID (44)	Identity systems handle PII; breaches may result in regulatory violations, reputational damage, and identity theft.
CWE-269: Improper Privilege Management	Government (11)	May result in unauthorized access to identity related administrative functions or role escalation.
CWE-284: Improper Access Control	Health (7), Finance (5), Government (11), Digital ID (52)	Can enable unauthorized modifications to identity attributes, access tokens, or policy enforcement logic.
CWE-285: Improper Authorization (Deprecated)	Finance (2), Government (7), Digital ID (85)	May allow unprivileged users to execute sensitive actions within ID platforms due to outdated or bypassed controls.
CWE-287: Improper Authentication	Health (7), Digital ID (165)	Critical to identity systems; failure to authenticate users properly may enable unauthorized access and impersonation.
CWE-288: Authentication Bypass Using an Alternate Path	Digital ID (36)	Identity workflows can be circumvented via unintended or undocumented paths, undermining trust in access control.
CWE-306: Missing Authentication for Critical Function	Digital ID (79)	High-risk flaw allowing execution of identity sensitive operations without authentication, risking full compromise.
CWE-352: Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF)	Health (19), Finance (3)	May allow attackers to forge actions such as profile edits, token resets, or role changes through authenticated sessions.
CWE-502: Deserialization of Untrusted Data	Health (5)	Can lead to remote code execution or object injection in identity services processing tokens or session data.
CWE-639: Insecure Direct Object Reference (IDOR)	Government (8), Finance (4), Digital ID (75)	May allow attackers to access or modify identity records by manipulating user-controllable identifiers.

CWE-707: Improper Enforcement of Message Integrity	Finance (2)	Affects identity assertions and token exchanges where integrity validation (e.g. JWT signature) is essential.
CWE-798: Use of Hardcoded Credentials	Health (6)	Undermines authentication systems if embedded credentials are leaked or reused across identity services.
CWE-862: Missing Authorization	Health (8), Finance (10), Government (7), Digital ID (94)	Indicates insecure API endpoints and logic flaws that allow identity operations without enforcing roles or policies.
CWE-863: Incorrect Authorization	Finance (5), Government (9), Digital ID (142)	Suggests misaligned or fragmented access control logic in identity layers, allowing privilege abuse.
CWE-918: Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF)	Government (4)	Could allow attackers to access internal identity services or metadata endpoints from external requests. May expose internal identity services or metadata APIs to unauthorized access.

As digital ID platforms increasingly underpin digital public infrastructure, maintaining their integrity requires proactive cross-sector threat intelligence and mitigation strategies grounded in CWE-driven root cause analysis.

4.6 Summary

The analysis indicates that Digital ID systems face a high concentration of authentication-related weaknesses and may also be indirectly exposed to vulnerability patterns emerging in adjacent sectors. The frequent appearance of common CWEs in the Finance, Health, and Government sectors points to shared architectural weaknesses that could affect integrated identity systems. Given their foundational role in digital public infrastructure, digital ID platforms require proactive, CWE-informed remediation strategies supported by cross-sector threat intelligence.

5 Strategic Considerations for DPI

Analysis of cross-sector CWE threats (Table 5) reveals that Digital ID systems face layered risks stemming from both infrastructure-level design limitations and application-level implementation flaws. Core identity functions are particularly vulnerable to authorisation-related flaws such as CWE-284 (Improper Access Control), CWE-285 (Improper Authorisation), CWE-862 (Missing Authorisation), and CWE-863 (Incorrect Authorization), all of which compromise role enforcement and privilege boundaries. These are exacerbated by injection vulnerabilities such as CWE-89 (SQL Injection) and CWE-79 (XSS), which may lead to credential exposure, session hijacking, or unauthorised access in identity-related workflows [42; 21]. Additionally, CWE-200 (Information Exposure) and CWE-352 (CSRF) demonstrate how data protection and secure user interactions remain critical challenges. The presence of CWE-918 (SSRF) and CWE-20 (Input Validation) further highlights systemic gaps in request handling and input sanitation that can be exploited in identity verification flows. To mitigate these risks, identity platforms must adopt a security-by-design strategy that ensures least privilege access, secure session management, rigorous input validation, and continuous authorisation checks across APIs and service layers [31; 18]. Regular code audits and automated vulnerability scanning aligned with CWE mappings can enhance coverage of systemic weaknesses and reduce long-term risk across identity infrastructures.

5.1 Implications of Attack Vectors

As identity systems evolve into critical connective infrastructure including Government, Finance, Health, and other social services, their attack surface now extends far beyond isolated login endpoints - encompassing APIs, biometric modules, authentication or APIs, identity providers, and real-time session handlers [43; 11].

The dominance of the *Network* attack vector in all sectors, and especially within Digital ID environments, underscores the exposure of remotely accessible identity services, which consistently account for the majority of CVE reporting across sectors. As national ID platforms, e-signature gateways, and authentication services continue to move online, they simultaneously expand both citizen access and adversary reach. The steady increase in *Network* based CVEs suggests an urgent need to harden Internet-facing components, particularly IAM interfaces, OAuth/OIDC flows, and session-token endpoints, against volume-driven risks. Any lapse in these areas could compromise foundational DPI services, from delivery to digital voting.

In particular, the gradual increase in the *Local* and *Adjacent Networks* vectors in digital ID systems mirrors the trends observed in Health and Government infrastructures [35; 33; 22]. This mirrors broader sector trends and may reflect increasing research attention to lateral movement, misconfigured trust boundaries, and edge node exposures. These trends raise concerns for identity systems deployed in on-premise environments, such as hospitals, municipal data centres, or hybrid cloud setups, where a single *Local* exploit could cascade into privilege escalation or authentication bypass within the DPI stack.

The low but persistent presence of *Physical* attacks within digital identification systems is also of disproportionate importance. Although rare, breaches can have irreversible consequences, particularly for systems involving biometric data, hardware tokens (e.g., smartcards) or cryptographic key stores [30; 42]. A successful *Physical* vector compromise can undermine the trustworthiness at the root of an identity ecosystem, reversing the validity of every transaction, signature or claim derived from it.

Cross-sectoral trends highlight the urgent need to treat Digital ID not as a standalone function but as a critical infrastructure embedded deeply in every domain of public service delivery. Identity systems now function as amplifiers of risk: their compromise can spread across service layers, affecting healthcare access, financial authorisations, and legal documentation processes [40; 10].

Strategic Defensive Priorities

The findings highlight a clear policy and architectural imperative: to implement attack vector-specific defences that are tailored to how Digital ID systems are integrated within each sector. Based on observed attack vector patterns, the following priorities can strengthen Digital ID infrastructures:

- *Network*-layer segmentation and API security for externally facing authentication services.

- Endpoint hardening and runtime monitoring for *Local* and *Physical* node identities.
- Secure boot chains, tamper detection, and physical access controls for biometric and credential issuance systems.
- Continuous cross-sector threat modelling to anticipate CWEs from high-volume sectors such as Health and Finance.

In summary, the shifting attack vector landscape calls for a reconceptualisation of identity security - not merely as access control but as systemic risk containment. As the digital public infrastructure becomes more interdependent, the security of identity systems will play an increasingly fundamental role in national digital resilience.

5.2 Implications of CWEs

The sectoral distribution of CWEs not only reveals the types of vulnerability affecting different domains, but also serves as a mirror to their evolving digital architectures and operational priorities. The dominance of authentication and authorisation flaws in Digital ID systems, juxtaposed with injection, input validation, and session management weaknesses in Health, Finance, and Government, signals a growing convergence of risk across digital ecosystems [29; 21].

Digital ID platforms increasingly function as a shared infrastructure, enabling access to e-health, e-banking, social protection, and administrative services. This interconnectedness means that a vulnerability that originates in one sector - for example, SQL Injection into a health record portal - may offer entry points into other identity-related systems, especially when access is mediated through centralised authentication platforms, especially when login or centralised identity and access management systems are involved.

The widespread presence of CWEs (Improper Authentication, Missing Authorisation, and Incorrect Authorisation) in Digital ID systems highlights structural fragility in the enforcement of identity verification and access policies. These weaknesses are particularly alarming given the growing reliance on Digital ID for national service delivery, digital onboarding, and cross-border eKYC processes. A compromise in these areas not only risks unauthorised access it also undermines trust in public-facing platforms that depend on robust identity assurance.

Furthermore, the presence of CWE categories such as Information Exposure, Cross-Site Scripting, and Server-side Request Forgery across Government, Finance, and Health systems suggests emerging threats to data integrity and backend security. These CWEs can indirectly compromise Digital ID systems by exploiting weak integrations, metadata exposures, or misconfigured authorisation flows, particularly in microservice or API-based environments that are common in modern digital public infrastructures [20; 19].

Importantly, this analysis reveals that Digital ID systems are not isolated targets, but rather points of convergence where multi-sector threats manifest. As these systems extend their presence to mobile apps, kiosks, and cross-sector service delivery channels, the attack surface becomes larger and more heterogeneous. Biometric data, identity tokens, and session cookies become high-value assets sought after, not just by opportunistic attackers, but by well-resourced threat actors [44; 12; 30].

To mitigate these risks, a shift is required—from isolated patching to cross-sector vulnerability anticipation. Digital Public Infrastructure architects should:

- Leverage CWE-based threat intelligence from adjacent sectors to prevent risks before they enter the identity layer.
- Apply differential security controls for high-risk CWEs such as SQL Injection and Cross-Site Scripting, especially in federated identity and API gateways.
- Prioritise identity-specific hardening (e.g., multilayer authorisation checks, access scope validation, token hygiene) in systems that interlink with health, finance, or government services.

- Institute common governance mechanisms to ensure rapid disclosure, shared mitigation, and collective monitoring of cross-sector vulnerabilities.

Ultimately, the security posture of Digital ID platforms will increasingly define the security of Digital Public Infrastructure as a whole. Their role as both enabler and validator means that any breach reverberates through multiple dependent systems. Proactive, CWE-informed risk modelling across sectoral boundaries must therefore be viewed not just as a security measure, but as a foundational component of digital trust and national cyber sovereignty.

5.3 Mapping Sectoral Vulnerabilities

The Sankey visualizations in Appendix A (Figures 9, 10, 11, and 12) map CVEs related to the Digital ID, Healthcare, Government, and Finance sectors. They highlight structural patterns and raise key questions about the current vulnerability landscape. By illustrating connections between CVE assigners, vendors, affected products, and attack vectors, these visualisations reveal both sector-specific concentrations and broader systemic exposure pathways.

5.3.1 Sector-Specific Observations

Each sector exhibits unique structural traits in its vulnerability ecosystem:

- **Digital Identity** is strongly influenced by major vendors such as Cisco, IBM, and Fortinet. This underscores the central role of identity services within network infrastructure and the heightened exposure from Internet-facing IAM components [23; 20].
- **Healthcare** shows a fragmented vendor landscape, with a mix of small vendors, open-source projects (e.g., *PHPGurukul*, *SourceCodester*), and limited representation of large commercial players. The high concentration of vulnerabilities in products such as hospital and blood bank systems suggests reliance on custom or legacy software stacks, many of which may lack structured patch management or formal security oversight [41].
- **Government** mappings reflect a similarly fragmented ecosystem, including both open-source platforms (e.g., *Nextcloud*, *Decidim*) and enterprise solutions (e.g., *IBM*, *Grafana*). Interestingly, a broader distribution across attack vectors—particularly *Local* and *Physical*— suggests diverse exposure types across government systems, possibly reflecting a mix of legacy platforms and newer public-facing services [45].
- **Finance** stands out for its centralised reliance on a small number of dominant vendors, particularly *Oracle* and *IBM*. The heavy use of proprietary enterprise software results in large vulnerability clusters, but likely benefiting from more formal vulnerability disclosure processes and patching workflows, due to the dominance of regulated, proprietary platforms [21].

5.3.2 Cross-Sector Patterns

Across all sectors, *Network*-based attack vectors are overwhelmingly dominant. While this likely reflects the Internet-exposed nature of modern digital services, it may also indicate reporting bias or limited visibility into multivector attacks. The lower prevalence of *Local*, *Physical*, and *Adjacent Network* vectors could reflect under reporting or misclassification, particularly for complex multistage attack scenarios [45; 46; 47].

Another important observation is the visibility and reporting role of assigners like *GitHub*, *VulDB*, and *Oracle*. The strong influence of assigners like GitHub, VulDB, and Oracle, especially in open-source environments, suggests that vulnerability discovery and disclosure in some sectors (e.g., Government and Health) are largely community-driven. This raises questions about potential underreporting in proprietary systems, where limited transparency or inactive disclosure programs may mask systemic issues [48]

The granularity and consistency of product naming across diagrams also emerge as a challenge. Inconsistent labelling (e.g., generic terms like “security-advisories” or ambiguous project names) reduces the analytic

clarity of product-level vulnerability tracking. Introducing naming normalization or mapping to CPEs could greatly enhance cross-sector comparability. Future work should incorporate mapping these flows against frameworks like *MITRE ATT&CK* could provide strategic insight into adversary behaviour and defence planning [49; 45].

5.4 DPI and Public Value

As governments and industries increasingly rely on digital identity and related infrastructures, it is important to frame these systems. Digital Identity and authentication platforms must be treated not merely as software stacks, but as DPI with broad societal and economic implications. The Economics of Shared Digital Infrastructures report by [50] argues that traditional cost-benefit approaches often fail to capture the systemic value of digital infrastructure—especially those foundational to service delivery, interoperability, and sector-wide integration. Instead, such systems should be evaluated in terms of their interoperability, standardisation, and ability to generate spillover effects across sectors. Many of the vulnerabilities observed, particularly in fragmented Government and Healthcare systems, can be viewed as structural outcomes of siloed development strategies, where systems were not originally designed for interoperability, reuse, or scalable governance [50; 26]. Integrating the DPI lens into vulnerability management could therefore help prioritise investments in modular, secure, and interoperable systems that generate long-term public value, rather than short-term functional fixes.

5.5 Linking DPI Readiness to Sectoral Vulnerabilities

The DPI Map codebook [43] provides critical context for assessing both the maturity and the regulatory framework of the digital identity, real-time payment, and data exchange infrastructures across countries. For example, in sectors such as Healthcare and Government, where fragmented systems and open source tools dominate the CVE landscape, the codebook indicates that many countries still lack fully implemented national digital ID frameworks, data exchange layers, or standardised authentication mechanisms [51]. This inconsistent maturity of infrastructure may partially explain the high concentration of CVE in loosely governed or fragmented systems, such as hospital and municipal services [25; 50]. Similarly, while the financial sector shows increased vendor concentration and use of proprietary software, the existence of real-time payment systems with cross-domain capabilities (e.g., interbank and mobile money) implies greater reliance on interoperable infrastructure, but also a larger attack surface for network-based exploits [50]. As shown in the DPI Map codebook, variables such as “Active real-time payment system present” and “Base technical architecture” for data exchange help identify whether foundational DPI systems are present or are still in early pilot phases. This highlights a structural link between the prevalence of CVEs and gaps in the implementation of secure, interoperable DPI layers, particularly in less mature sectors or early-stage deployments [51].

5.6 Summary

Foundational and functional Digital ID systems demonstrate greater vulnerability than sector-specific functional systems in Finance, Health, and Government. This is reflected in the significantly higher volume of reported vulnerabilities in Digital ID platforms and the concentration of weaknesses affecting core identity functions such as authentication and access control. Unlike Finance and Health, where many issues relate to domain-specific applications or data handling, vulnerabilities in Digital ID systems often target the mechanisms that enable access across sectors. These foundational weaknesses not only affect identity platforms directly but also propagate through their integration with Financial, Healthcare, and Government services. As such, Digital ID serves both as an attack surface and a risk amplifier. However, further analysis is required to understand the specific technologies, products, vendors, and services adopted in functional versus foundational Digital ID systems, in order to precisely pinpoint where vulnerabilities are concentrated. These patterns are often dependent on the architecture, deployment context, and integration depth of identity components within sectoral systems.

Moreover, this comparison highlights that sectors cannot address cybersecurity challenges in isolation. There are notable gaps in cross-sector operation that attackers could exploit. One gap is the lack of unified standards for software security across DPI – while finance has PCI and other standards, similar rigour is only now being considered for health and for government digital services. Additionally, inconsistent breach disclosure (as evidenced by the doubling of breach notices with no attack details hampers the ability of other

organizations to learn from incidents. The policy implication is that governments might need to mandate more detailed cyber incident reporting across all critical sectors, not just within each vertical. Another issue is the “weakest link” problem: well-resourced sectors like finance might invest in strong security, but their dependency on, say, a national ID system means they are still vulnerable if that ID system is weak. This calls for viewing DPI security as a public good: improvements in one sector’s security (like hardened digital ID protocols) benefit other sectors’ security.

6 Conclusion

The security of DPI is rapidly becoming a cornerstone of modern digital governance and trust. As this report has shown, the vulnerabilities that affect digital systems are not uniformly distributed—they are shaped by sector-specific architectures, operational dynamics, and the growing interdependence of systems anchored in digital identity. The aim and objectives outlined in Section 2 have been met through the systematic analysis presented in this report, which integrates CVE and CWE data, sector-specific filtering, attack vector classification, and product-level mapping. By combining CVE and CWE analysis with sector-specific filtering, attack vector classification, and product-level mapping through Sankey visualisations, this report offers a multidimensional view of the vulnerability landscape by combining CVE and CWE data, sector-specific filtering, attack vector analysis, and product-level mappings across Finance, Healthcare, and Government.

Digital identity systems are particularly vulnerable due to their central role in access management and their integration across critical sectors. Their dominant weaknesses—centered on authentication, authorisation, and access control—are compounded by vulnerabilities in the very systems they authenticate, connect, or govern. The propagation of weaknesses across Finance, Health, and Government platforms highlights how cross-sector weaknesses may propagate into identity systems, exposing them to inherited risks or cascading failures stemming from upstream platforms.

This analysis reinforces several key imperatives.

- **Adopt a cross-sector lens for vulnerability analysis.** Isolated threat monitoring overlooks the interconnectedness that characterises contemporary infrastructure.
- **Proactive vulnerability intelligence is essential.** Leveraging CWE trends and attack vectors provides anticipatory visibility into exploit paths, not just retrospective analysis.
- **Identity systems must be treated as critical national infrastructure.** Their compromise is not just a technical failure; it can lead to erosion of trust, service disruption, and systemic risk.

In the landscape of digital governance, the integrity of identity systems will increasingly define the trustworthiness and interoperability of DPIs. Looking ahead, emerging technologies (AI, quantum, etc.) would introduce novel weaknesses and risks that apply across these domains. Generative AI, for example, is already being used both by attackers (for crafting phishing content, deepfakes) and defenders (for threat detection) in numerous sectors. Ensuring that all DPI components can withstand future threats such as post-quantum cryptography needs, or AI-driven attack automation, will require a forward-looking, coordinated strategy. The literature recommends integrating security and development teams and promoting a culture of shared cyber responsibility. In essence, Digital ID, government, healthcare, and finance must advance together on the cybersecurity maturity curve; a weakness in one can undermine the public's trust in all. By addressing common weaknesses, sharing knowledge, and enforcing security governance across the DPI spectrum, stakeholders can better safeguard the foundational digital infrastructure on which modern societies will increasingly rely.

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Appendix A: Sankey Charts for Sectors

Digital Identity Mapping: Assigners → Vendor → Product → Attack Vector

Figure 9: Digital Identity Sector Sankey Chart: The Digital Identity sector Sankey diagram maps the assignment of vulnerabilities to vendors and key identity management products, culminating in their attack vectors. It reveals a concentration of vulnerabilities around major identity and authentication platforms such as Cisco Identity Services Engine and GitLab. The overwhelming dominance of network-based attacks in this sector underscores the critical importance of securing authentication pathways and federated identity services in digital public infrastructure.

Figure 10: Healthcare Sector Sankey Chart: The Healthcare sector Sankey diagram depicts how vulnerabilities flow from CVE assigners through vendors and healthcare management systems to attack vectors. It highlights a relatively fragmented vendor ecosystem with a focus on critical systems like hospital management platforms and online blood bank systems. The predominance of network-based attack vectors indicates widespread exposure risks to patient management and healthcare data systems, suggesting the need for improved cyber hygiene across healthcare IT ecosystems.

Government Sector Mapping: Assigners → Vendor → Product → Attack Vector

Figure 11: Government Sector Sankey Chart: The Government sector Sankey diagram maps vulnerabilities from their assignment through vendors and government service products to identified attack vectors. It shows a more distributed assignment landscape with multiple vendors and smaller-scale products like citizen digital certificates and government cyber services. The concentration of vulnerabilities leading to network-based attacks underlines common sectoral exposure points requiring enhanced protections for public-facing and inter-agency digital systems.

Finance Sector Mapping: Assigners → Vendor → Product → Attack Vector

Figure 12: Finance Sector Sankey Chart: The Finance sector Sankey diagram illustrates the flow of vulnerabilities from CVE assigners to vendors, associated financial products, and the attack vectors they expose. It highlights concentration points where specific vendors like Oracle dominate vulnerability assignments, emphasizing systemic risks around critical banking systems such as FLEXCUBE and SWIFT-related services. This visualization supports the identification of vendor-product clusters that are particularly susceptible to network-based attacks.